

PROGNOSTIC MODEL OF SUBSURFACE CONTAMINATION CAUSED BY NEW EMBANKMENTS ON THE TERRITORY OF MARITSA EAST COAL MINING COMPLEX – CENTRAL SOUTHERN BULGARIA

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ABSTRACT. One of the many environmental problems resulting from electricity generation in thermal power plants is the release of large amounts of solid wastes (coal combustion products). In the absence of effective eco-friendly disposal practices, this waste is accumulated in the form of coal ash embankments or in the excavated parts of the open-cast mines. The so constituted big landfills and surface impoundments emit leachate emissions containing a wide range of conventional pollutants among which, by definition, sulphate ions (SO_4) dominate. Using the computer program VS2DI, a numerical model is developed of the conditions for mass transport of pollutants (using the example of SO_4) from the designed new embankments for deposition of non-hazardous industrial solid waste from TPP in the area of the internal embankments of Troyanovo-North open-cast mine, part of the Maritsa East Coal Mining Complex. The scheme of convective-diffusion mass transport is employed, taking into account reversible elimination (sorption-desorption), mechanical dispersion and mixing. On the basis of the developed model, a long-term prognosis (100 years) is made for the extent and the degree of subsurface contamination from the new embankments. Based on the model solutions, the retention capacity of the geological foundation and the risk of groundwater pollution are assessed.

Keywords: environment protection, mass transport models, groundwater and soil contamination, landfills for solid waste from TPP, Maritsa East Coal Mining Complex.

Introduction

Despite their negative global impact on climate, environment and humans, fossil fuels (oil, gas and coal) still account for about 85% of the world energy sources, with only the share of coal being about 27% (BP statistical review of world energy, 2019). As a result, substantial amounts of extremely harmful carbon-containing containing waste gases, aerosols, liquid emissions and solid compounds are released into nature, which are the reason for air, water and soil contamination.

One of the largest sources of pollution worldwide is the generation of electricity in thermal power plants. Studies show that in addition to the notorious problem of air pollution related to this type of electricity generation, another serious challenge is the release of large amounts of residual products from coal combustion plants (CCPs).

Globally, the total volume of CCPs produced per year is about 1222 Mt, with China having the largest share - 565 Mt, India - 197 Mt and the United States - 107.4 Mt (Harris et al., 2020). At the same time, all European countries emit about 140 Mt per year, with the main share (about 100 Mt) falling on non-EU countries and Eastern European countries which joined the EU after 2004. Currently, the overall recycling rate of all CCPs is about 64%, with Japan leading the way - 99.3%, the EU15 - 94.3%, Israel - 90.9% and Korea - 85.4% (Harris et al., 2020). Unfortunately, the problem of CCPs still does not find good solutions in many Eastern European countries and in those outside the EU15.

The CCPs released during the generation of electricity in thermal power plants in coal mining complexes are usually deposited in the form of coal ash embankments or in the excavated parts of the open-cast mines. The leachate emissions produced by these landfills contain a wide range of conventional and priority pollutants, including B, SO_4 , Br, F, Cl, K, Na, Ca, As, Ba, Be, Cd, Cr, Co, Hg, Li, Mo, Pb, Sb, Se, Ti, and Ra^{226/228} (USEPA, 2009; EPRI, 2012, 2015; Hensel, 2016). When assessing the impact of CCPs on groundwater and soil, as principally typical and relatively highly mobile contaminants that enter the subsurface are regarded B, Mo, Li, SO_4 , Br, F, Cl, K,

Na, and Ca, and as most indicative amongst them are recognised B and SO_4 (EPRI, 2012; Rocha et al., 2017).

In Bulgaria, the main source of electricity generated in thermal power plants is the Maritsa East Coal Mining Complex, which is the largest one in South-eastern Europe. The coal mining complex includes several open-cast lignite mines – Troyanovo-1 Mine, Troyanovo-3 Mine, Troyanovo-North Mine, which supply coal to the large power plants built at the complex TPP AES Galabovo, TPP Maritza East 2 and TPP Maritsa East 3. The CCPs produced by these coal-fired thermoelectric power-production facilities are accumulated in the form of coal ash embankments built in the complex or in the excavated parts of the open-cast mines. The lignite used in electricity generation is characterised by extremely low calorific value, high ash content and very high sulphur content. This fact presupposes that the three thermal power plants emit huge amounts of solid residue not only from coal combustion, but also from flue gas desulphurisation facilities. Studies show that the consequences are severe and some problems, generating critical environmental issues, are present in the area of the coal mining complex, affecting all elements of the environment and human activity (Zheleva et al., 2004; Nikolova et al., 2010; Petrov, 2019).

The main task of the performed model studies is to achieve a quantitative prognosis for the extent and degree of possible subsurface contamination caused by liquid emissions incoming from the designed new embankments for deposition of CCPs from TPP AES Galabovo in the area of the internal embankments of Troyanovo-North Mine (Figure 1). According to the proposed approach, a two-dimensional (2D) numerical model of the conditions for mass transport of pollutants is developed, following the example of highly mobile sulphate ions (SO_4). One extremely severe assumption for a continuous inflow of pollutants from the new embankments over a period of 100 years is accepted in the model.

Based on the obtained model solutions, the retention capacity of the geological basement and the potential risk of groundwater pollution have been determined.

Fig. 1. Location of study area.

Methodological approach

The proposed methodological approach for predicting the possible spread and intensity of subsurface contamination caused by the embankments for deposition of CCPs implicates the use of two-dimensional computer models of fate and transport of pollutants in a variably saturated porous media. The development of these models is based on the following assumptions and general schemes for simulating the source of contamination, the studied part of the near-surface section, the processes of mass transport and the form of the model solutions:

(i) The conditions for mass transport of highly mobile pollutants are simulated on the example of SO_4 , which is considered as a key pollutant. The main reasons for this choice are: (a) this pollutant is among the most indicative ones when tracing CCPs leachate (EPRI, 2012); (b) it is conservative, moves at a pace comparable to the infiltration rate and marks the maximum spread of possible contamination in the subsurface area; (c) sulphate ions are easily soluble and have a high concentration in the new embankments.

(ii) The subsurface area is reconstructed with the specific parameters of the hydrogeological units established in the near-surface section: geometric parameters – top and bottom layers $z = f(x)$, average thickness m ; physical properties – density ρ , porosity n ; hydrodynamic properties – saturated hydraulic conductivity k , saturated water content θ_s , residual water content θ_r , unsaturated hydraulic conductivity function (relative hydraulic conductivity) k_r ; hydraulic characteristic functions – relations between pressure head h , moisture content θ and relative hydraulic conductivity k_r ; mass transport parameters – distribution coefficient of the key pollutant $K_D^{SO_4}$, dispersivity α , molecular diffusion D_M , coefficient of irreversible elimination γ .

(iii) The groundwater recharge by infiltration and percolation is set in accordance with the specific climatic, soil and technogenic conditions.

(iv) The mechanism of the mass transport of pollutants is in its full form: convective transport accompanied by reversible elimination (adsorption and ion exchange), irreversible elimination (precipitation or decay), mechanical dispersion (longitudinal and transverse), molecular diffusion and mixing.

(v) The potential surface contaminator simulated in the mathematical models is set as a line source of pollution. The concentration of SO_4 in the CCPs leachate is set as a constant value for the entire period of the simulation $C_p^{SO_4} = \text{const}$.

(vi) In order to simplify the model, the following reasonably conservative assumptions are also accepted: the infiltration rate is constant over the entire model area, and the concentration of SO_4 is homogeneously distributed along the entire length of the simulated surface pollution source. Of course, if the landfill project contains detailed data on the scheme, the quantitative parameters and the rates of deposition activities, it is appropriate to take them into account by introducing appropriate stress periods and corresponding changes in the boundary conditions.

(vii) The results of the model calculations are presented as relative concentrations of SO_4 (in %), i.e. as a ratio between the current concentration $C_t^{SO_4}$ at a specific moment t and the initial (input) concentration $C_p^{SO_4}$. Normally, the value $C_p^{SO_4} = 100\%$ is set as initial concentration over the entire spread of the new embankment and the background concentration in the subsurface section is set as $C_b^{SO_4} = 0\%$.

(viii) It is expedient to perform long-term prognostic calculations, i.e. the period of computer simulations shall be not less than 50 years.

Modelling tools

The mathematical 2D model of the conditions for the mass transport of pollutants in a variably saturated porous media is compiled with the software package VS2DTI Version 1.3 (Lappala et al., 1987; Healy, 1990; Hsieh et al., 2000). The algorithm of the programme uses a numerical finite difference method to solve the flow equation and the advection-dispersion equation (Bear, 1979; Healy, 1990).

The relations between pressure head, moisture content and relative hydraulic conductivity can be modelled using the functions proposed by van Genuchten (1980), Brooks and Corey (1964), Haverkamp et al. (1977), Rossi and Nimmo (1994), or by published values.

The initial hydraulic conditions are specified with a static equilibrium profile setting either the pressure head or the moisture content.

The boundary conditions include setting of the pressure head or the total head, as well as flow rate, recharge from infiltration, evaporation, transpiration, and boundary flow-through elements.

The processes describing mass transport include convective transport, molecular and mechanical dispersion, reversible elimination, irreversible elimination, and mixing. The processes that are the reason for a substance to enter/leave the liquid phase are simulated in two ways: (a) the dissolved mass is introduced into (or removed from) the model region by setting a certain concentration of the pollutant in the inflow or outflow boundary conditions; (b) the change in the concentration of the pollutant is simulated by the Henry linear isotherm, the Freundlich isotherm or the Langmuir isotherm, which describe the chemical reactions in the liquid phase or the reactions between the liquid and solid phases.

Conceptual model

The mathematical model for estimating the potential subsurface contamination caused by the designed new CCPs landfills in the area of the internal embankments of Trayanovo-North open-cast mine is developed in accordance with the following prerequisites:

(i) Model area. Comprises the hydrogeological section in the range of the designed new embankments along Line 278 in the section from m+35200 to m+36000 (Figure 2).

(ii) Hydrogeological units (HGU). As illustrated in Figure 2, two low-rank hydrogeological units are established in the near-surface section – upper low-permeability anthropogenic layer (HGU1) and lower low-permeability layer (HGU2). The upper anthropogenic layer is an old embankment of mixed materials - clay from the overburden and CCPs. The landfill materials are uncompact and highly inhomogeneous, which presupposes their hydrodynamic heterogeneity and trend of differential

settlement. The embankments thickness is usually between 25 and 30 m. The lower layer covers part of the intact clay-sand Neogene complex. It is represented mainly by Neogene clays and silty clays with calcareous inclusions. Layers and lenses of fine-grained and clayey sands are rarely observed in depth. The studied segment of the old embankment can be regarded as a part of the unsaturated zone. According to borehole data, the static groundwater levels are registered at an elevation of about 45-46 m in single lenses and seams in the intact Neogene complex.

Fig. 2. Conceptual framework of the two-dimensional models

1 – New embankment; 2 – Upper low-permeability anthropogenic layer (Model zone MZ 1); 3 – Lower low-permeability layer (Model zone MZ 2); 4 – Groundwater level; 5 – Rainfall infiltration; 6 – Leachate infiltration.

Table 1. Physical, hydrodynamic and mass transport field characteristics of the hydrogeological units

Hydrological unit (HGU)	Model zone №	Volumetric mass density ρ_n , mg/m ³	Porosity n , -	Hydraulic conductivity k , m/d	Longitudinal dispersivity α_L , m	Molecular diffusion coefficient D_M , m ² /d	Distribution coefficient $K_D^{SO_4}$, cm ³ /g
HGU1	MZ1	2.0E+09	4.3E-01	2.5E-02	1.5E00	7.5E-04	3.1E-10
HGU2	MZ2	1.85E+09	5.0E-01	4.8E-03	8.0E-01	3.5E-04	4.9E-10

Remark: Main sources of the implemented averaged values of ρ_n , n , k , α_L , D_M , and $K_D^{SO_4}$: (1) Stoyanov, 2007, 2019; (2) Spitz and Moreno, 1996; (3) Adams and Gelhar, 1996; (4) Enviro Base – software product of Waterloo Hydrogeologic Inc., Ontario Canada; (5) Unpublished data.

(iii) Hydrogeological parameters. The hydraulic conductivity k and the physical characteristics (density ρ , porosity n , etc.) of the two layers are defined according to data from in-situ observations and laboratory tests conducted for the study area (slug tests, tracer tests, granulometric analysis, petrophysical analysis, etc.). The distribution coefficient K_D (respectively, the sorption porosity n_s) reflecting the fate of SO_4 in the upper low-permeability anthropogenic layer is defined according to data acquired by conducted laboratory tests (tracer tests) with materials from Gypsum storage facility №1 of TPP Maritsa East 2 (Stoyanov, 2007). The mass transport field characteristics (distribution coefficient K_D , longitudinal dispersion α_L , molecular diffusion coefficient D_M) of the hydrogeological units, which are not laboratory established, are determined according to literature data for similar soil types (Adams and Gelhar, 1992; Spitz and Moreno, 1996; Enviro Base, 2003; Stoyanov, 2019). The values of the physical, hydrodynamic and mass transport characteristics, applied in the prognostic model, are presented in Table 1.

(iv) Rainfall recharge.

Infiltration rate W_b . With an average annual value of precipitation of 550 mm and an average annual air temperature of 12.3 °C, the total discharge (surface and underground) is 186 mm/a. The infiltration rate, calculated according to Bredencamp (1990) for low-permeability soils, is 31 mm/a. It follows that the infiltration recharge is about 5.6% of the precipitation. Therefore, the infiltration rate W_b is equal to 8.5E-5 m/d.

Concentration of sulphate ions in rainfall. With some conditionality, it is accepted that the presence of sulphate ions in precipitation is negligible, i.e. $C_b^{SO_4} = 0\%$.

(v) Source of contamination. This is the landfill leachate as illustrated in Figure 2. The model considers the fate and transport of the selected key pollutant SO_4 . The accepted values for the leachate infiltration rate W_p and for the concentration of sulphate ions $C_p^{SO_4}$ over the entire area of the source are as follows:

Leachate infiltration rate W_p . As precipitation is the only income element in the new embankments water balance, it is

assumed that it is equal to the groundwater recharge from infiltration, i.e. $W_p = 8.5E-5$ m/d.

Concentration of sulphate ions in leachate $C_p^{SO_4}$. According to the established way of presenting the model prognostications in relative concentrations, it is accepted that in leachate $C_p^{SO_4} = 100\%$.

(vi) Period of computer simulations. Taking into account the very low water permeability of the two hydrogeological units, one can expect that the rate of mass transport processes will be low. Therefore, it is recommendable for the prognostic models of possible subsurface contamination to cover a period of 100 years.

Composition of the prognostic model

For structuring the prognostic model, the VS2DTI programme and the main prerequisites presented in the conceptual model are used.

The mathematical model is two-dimensional. It reproduces the fate and transport of highly mobile contaminants in the section along the profile illustrated in Figure 2. The determined low-rank hydrogeological units are simulated with two model zones MZ1 and MZ2. Each zone is set with its geometry and hydrodynamic and mass transport field characteristics corresponding to the real ones (Table 1).

An orthogonal grid with cell dimensions of 0.5 x 2.0 m is utilised for the spatial discretisation of the model area. The time of the computer simulation is divided into 100 stress periods, each lasting 1 year.

The relationship between pressure head, moisture content and relative hydraulic conductivity is modelled using the functions proposed by van Genuchten. In this case, for the variable residual moisture content (RMC) and for the isotherm parameters α and β are used incorporated in the computer programme values for similar types of soil. The Henry linear isotherm is applied in order to model the solid-liquid reactions.

The initial hydraulic condition is specified as an equilibrium profile, which is set as the initial pressure head equals negative elevation head above a water table.

Along the lateral boundaries of the model in the saturated part of HGU2, according to the established groundwater levels, a boundary condition *Specified total head* is set, and in the unsaturated part of HGU1 and HGU2, a boundary condition *Possible seepage face* is accepted.

The upper boundary of the model area follows the elevation of the old embankment. It is divided into 3 parts – a central one, having a length of 560 m and two peripheral, having lengths of 150 m and 90 m, respectively. The central part outlines the bottom of the new embankment, where the leachate emissions come from, i.e. it marks the linear source of contamination.

A boundary condition *Specified flux into domain* is set along the upper boundary of the model area with the following input data: (a) in the central part of the profile, during the whole period of the model simulation, the pollutants enter with infiltration rate $W_p = 8.5E-5$ m/d and input concentration of sulphate ions $C_p^{SO_4} = 100\%$; (b) in the peripheral parts of the profile, during the whole period of the model simulation, pure rainwater enters with infiltration rate $W_b = 8.5E-5$ m/d and concentration of sulphate ions $C_b^{SO_4} = 0\%$.

Results and discussion

With the developed model, at the end of each stress period, a prognosis is made for the extent and degree of possible subsurface contamination. The results of the computer simulations of the fate and transport of the most mobile pollutants are illustrated with the obtained model solutions, presented in Figure 3, reflecting the distribution of sulphate ions after a period of 5, 50, and 100 years.

The model is also used in order to calculate the depth of the polluted zone $D_p^{SO_4}$ (the contamination front) as a function of time $D_p^{SO_4} = f(t_i)$ in the lowest part of the terrain – the sector at m+35685. The calculations are performed tracking the isoline of sulphate ions concentration $C_p^{SO_4} = 0.5\%$. The obtained results are illustrated in Figure 4.

Based on the model solutions, a long-term prognosis can be made for the subsurface contamination beneath the new embankment. The mobile pollutants that have entered the old embankment move very slowly and the main direction of mass transfer is vertical. In 100 years, the pollution front advances to a depth of about 18-19 m, i.e. the vertical velocity of the pollutants is very low - about 5 mm/d.

The most intense contamination affects the upper part of the old embankment to a depth of 3-4 m, where the concentration of SO_4 is between 75 and 100%. At depths above 10-11 m, the values of SO_4 concentration fall below 10%. The contaminated zone expands laterally by about 5 m due to the processes of molecular diffusion and mechanical dispersion.

For the forecast period (100 years), the pollution will be limited in the old embankments and will not reach the intact clay-sand Neogene complex. Thus, there is no risk of groundwater contamination, taking into account also the low water permeability of the Neogene clays that compose HGU2. The main reason for the slow rate of the mass transfer processes and the limited spread of the contaminated area is the very low water permeability and the large thickness of the old embankment of mixed materials – clay from the overburden and CCPs.

Conclusion

The solutions obtained with the developed prognostic model show that for a period of 100 years the subsurface contamination caused by the designed new embankments in the area of Troyanovo-North open-cast mine will cover only part of the old embankments without affecting the intact clay-sand Neogene complex. There is no risk of groundwater pollution. In hydrogeological aspect, the terrain is completely appropriate for deposition of coal combustion products from TPP AES Galabovo.

The presented prognostic model illustrates the great efficiency of the proposed methodological approach for preliminary assessments of the possible contamination of near-surface section and groundwater caused by landfills for deposition of CCPs, produced by coal-fired thermoelectric power-production facilities.

Our experience confirms that the same approach can be successfully applied in solving similar hydrogeological and environmental problems.

Fig. 3. Results of the computer simulations of the subsurface contamination caused by the new embankment

Fig. 4. Depth of the contamination front in the lowest part of the terrain – the sector at m+35685

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References

Adams E., Gelhar L., 1992. Field study of dispersion in a heterogeneous aquifer. 2. Spatial moments analysis, *Water Resour. Res.*, 28 (12), 3293-3307.

Bear J. 1979. *Hydraulics of groundwater*. New York, McGraw-Hill, 569 p.

BP statistical review of world energy 2019. 68th edition. 64 p. Available at: <https://www.bp.com/content/dam/bp/business-sites/en/global/corporate/pdfs/energy-economics/statistical-review/bp-stats-review-2019-full-report.pdf>.

Bredenkamp D. 1990. Quantitative estimation of groundwater recharge by means of a simple rainfall-recharge relationship, in: *Groundwater recharge*, IAH Memoir, 8, ed. D. Lerner, A. Issar, I. Simmers, Heise, 247–256.

- Brooks R., Corey A., 1964. Hydraulic properties of porous media, in: Hydrology Papers 3, Colorado State University, Fort Collins, 27 p.
- Electric Power Research Institute (EPRI) 2012. Groundwater Quality Signatures for Assessing Potential Impacts from Coal Combustion Product Leachate, Technical Report 1017923, 162 p.
- Electric Power Research Institute (EPRI) 2015. Groundwater Monitoring Guidance for the Coal Combustion Residuals Rule, Technical Report 3002006287, 172 p.
- Haverkamp R., Vauclin M., Tovina J., Wierenga P., Vachaud G., 1977. A comparison of numerical simulation models for one-dimensional infiltration, Soil Science Society of America Journal, 41 (2), 285-294.
- Healy R. W., 1990. Simulation of solute transport in variably saturated porous media with supplemental information on modifications to the US Geological Survey's computer program VS2D, USGS Numb. Ser., Water-Resour. Inv. Rep. 90-4025, Colorado, 125 p.
- Hensel B., 2016. Groundwater Monitoring and Data Analysis under the Coal Combustion Residuals Rule, Coal Combustion and Gasification Products, 9, 37-41.
- Hsieh P., Wingle W., Healy R. W., 2000. VS2DI - A graphical software package for simulating fluid flow and solute or energy transport in variably saturated porous media, USGS Numb. Ser., Water-Resour. Inv. Rep. 99-4130, 16 p.
- Lappala E., Healy R., Weeks E. 1987. Documentation of computer program VS2D to solve the equations of fluid flow in variably saturated porous media. USGS, Water-Resour. Inv. Rep. 83-4099, Colorado, 184 p.
- Nikolova M., Gerganov G., Sirashki G., Sirashki H., Ivanov V., 2010. Vlianie na energijnia kompleks "Maritsa Istok" varhu proizvodstvoto na ekologichna zemedelska produktsia, Scientific Research Almanac, 13, 419-471 (in Bulgarian with English abstract)
- Petrov P. 2019. Oharakterizirane na otpadatsite ot TETs "Svilozha" i tiahnoto ekologosabrazno sahranenie i opolzotvoriavane. Avangard Prima, Sofia, 139 p. (in Bulgarian)
- Rocha A., Smith J., Graves D., Biogeochemistry: A novel approach to managing and marketing CCR, Proc. of World of Coal Ash (WOCA) Conference in Lexington, May 9-11, 2017, KY, USA.
- Rossi C., Nimmo J., 1994. Modeling of soil water retention from saturation to oven dryness, Water Resource Research, 30 (3), 701-708.
- Spitz, K., Moreno J. 1996. A practical guide to groundwater and solute modeling. JW&S, NY, 460 p.
- Stoyanov N. 2019. Matematicheskoto modelirane v hidrogeologiyata. Chisleni 3D modeli po metoda na krainite razliki. Vanio Nedkov, Sofia, 246 p. (in Bulgarian)
- Stoyanov N., 2007. Migratsionni harakteristiki na tvardia otpadak (pepinata), otdelian pri eksploatatsiata na TETs, Annual of the University of Mining and Geology "St. Ivan Rilski", 50, Part 1, 177-182 (in Bulgarian with English abstract)
- Zheleva E., Tsoleva M., Bogdanov B., 2004. Novi ekologichni i tehicheski problemi pri rekultivatsiata na narushenite tereni ot mini "Maritsa Istok", Management and sustainable development, 1-2 (10), 323-328 (in Bulgarian with English abstract)
- U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (US EPA) 2009. Statistical Analysis of Groundwater Monitoring Data at RCRA Facilities: Unified Guidance. – EPA 530/R-09-007, 884 p.
- van Genuchten M. Th., 1980. A closed-form equation for predicting the hydraulic conductivity of unsaturated soils, Soil Science Society of America Journal, 44 (5), 892-898.